

Differences in perception of AI-supported CV screening processes between cohorts in the recruiting process: a scoping review protocol

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Abstract

Background: The increasing integration of AI into recruiting processes is fundamentally changing how employers identify and evaluate potential applicants. While AI-supported CV screening processes aim to increase efficiency and objectivity through semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking, limited empirical evidence exists regarding how applicants from different generational cohorts perceive and evaluate this technology. This scoping review therefore examines cohort-specific differences in the perception of AI-supported CV screening processes and the resulting evidence gaps to identify future research directions.

Methods: The scoping review is conducted according to the methodology of the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) and follows the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews (PRISMA-ScR) to ensure methodological stringency, transparency, and reproducibility. A comprehensive search is conducted in the electronic database and platform EBSCO, Scopus, and IEEE Xplore. These databases and platforms provide access to a wide range of peer-reviewed articles and enable precise literature searches through their extensive search environments. The review design was chosen to identify interdisciplinary literature on the topics of cohorts, recruiting through AI-supported CV screening processes, semantic matching, cut-off threshold ranking, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Generational Cohort Theory (GCT). Considering the diversity of study designs, a scoping review is a valuable approach for systematically capturing the range and complexity of this research field. Titles/abstracts as well as full-text reviews will be screened by two independent reviewers based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the review to confirm eligibility. Discrepancies will be resolved through discussion, involving a third reviewer where necessary. Study characteristics will be summarized in a table format together with thematic analyses. Furthermore, narrative summaries of key elements related to AI-supported CV screening processes and semantic matching, cut-off threshold ranking, and the dimensions of TAM and GCT will be recorded and listed.

Expected Outcomes: This scoping review aims to provide valuable insights into cohort-specific value orientations and the perception and acceptance of AI-supported processes in recruiting, drawing on the TAM dimensions of Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) as the primary evaluative framework. Consequently, this scoping review aims to (1) systematically map interdisciplinary research at the interface of technology acceptance and AI-supported CV screening across generational cohorts, (2) identify how cohort-specific value orientations may shape PU and PEOU of semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking, and (3) derive theoretically grounded propositions that inform future qualitative and quantitative primary research on AI-based selection processes.

Keywords: AI-supported recruiting processes, semantic matching, technology acceptance model, generational cohort theory, cut-off threshold ranking, CV screening

Introduction:

Recruiting is a central process in human resources management for companies and organizations (Rojas-Galeano et al., 2022). The aim is to attract suitable and screen out unsuitable applicants along the hiring funnel as described by (Bogen & Rieke, 2018). This hiring funnel comprises the phases of search, pre-selection, interview, and selection, during which decisions are made regarding potential applicants. These decision-making processes are increasingly supported using artificial intelligence (AI). AI-supported tools¹ such as chatbots or systems based on natural language processing (NLP) are designed to reduce implicit human biases (Bower et al., 2017; Chowdhury, 2003). Research shows that algorithmic automated decision-making processes can lead to various forms of unequal treatment (Bogen & Rieke, 2018). They do not make autonomous decisions, but rather execute human-defined rules technically. This creates close interaction between humans and machines, with both technical parameters and human decision-making logic influencing the outcome.

These systems are primarily used in the screening stage, where application documents such as resumes (Curriculum Vitae - CV) are evaluated using semantic matching and cut-off threshold rankings. The software analyzes not only key terms, but also meanings, synonyms, and contexts to evaluate matches with the applicant profile. The resulting score serves as a cut-off threshold value used to decide whether applicants advance to the next stage (interviewing) of the process. This algorithmic selection process is not transparent to applicants and can lead to misjudgments, if the basis for the algorithmic decision is not comprehensive. The screening stage, in which the initial decision-making preselection takes place, is increasingly becoming the focus of scientific and practical considerations. Studies by (Alonso et al., 2025) and (Ajjam & Al-Raweshidy, 2026) describe the technological basis of these systems, which are based on deep learning transformers and calculate semantic similarities between texts. There is broad consensus within the research community that these methods increase efficiency and objectivity in recruiting by overcoming the limitations of traditional keyword-based approaches and accelerating the pre-selection process (Horodyski, 2023). Nevertheless, there are clear differences in the assessment of fairness, validity, and susceptibility to bias in such systems. While some authors argue that AI-supported screening processes have the potential to reduce discrimination and increase the validity of selection decisions, other studies highlight the emergence of novel forms of algorithmic bias (Chouldechova & Roth, 2018; Köchling et al., 2021).

These result from use of historical training data that is influenced by human bias and does not reduce existing inequalities, but potentially reinforces them (Ajjam & Al-Raweshidy, 2026). In this context, empirical findings show that younger applicants, are more accepting of digital selection processes. This is evident in the early stage of the hiring funnel, such as screening, where algorithmic processes are

¹ The reference to Appendix 3, Article 6, Sentence 2, Point 4 of the EU Artificial Intelligence Regulation 2024/1689: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/TXT/HTML/?uri=OJ:L_202401689#anx_III

perceived as more objective and less prone to error than human decisions (Horodyski, 2023; Tursunbayeva et al., 2025).

The Population, Concept, and Context (PCC) framework (Peters et al., 2020) serves as a guide for the proposed scoping review and is based on the assumption that technological acceptance is not a homogeneous construct, but is significantly influenced by cohort-specific values and socio-technical experiences. Empirical research remains limited regarding how different cohorts evaluate semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking processes in terms of Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) as defined by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and what expectations they derive from this for employers (Horodyski, 2023). While perceived fairness, transparency, and trust are frequently discussed in the AI-recruiting literature, their relationship to cohort-specific technology acceptance remains underexplored.

Previous research has focused primarily on technological aspects and has mostly addressed acceptance issues at an aggregate level, without systematically considering the cohort-specific values and experiences with technology. The scoping review aims to explore this research gap by examining the perception of AI-supported screening processes from a cross-cohort perspective. The scoping review focuses on the mechanisms of semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking, which significantly determine the evaluation and pre-selection of applicants. The combination of the Generational Cohort Theory (GCT) and the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) creates a theoretical frame of reference that makes it possible to explain and empirically capture cohort-specific differences in perception and acceptance. GCT provides the lens for identifying cohort-specific value patterns, while the TAM core variables PU and PEOU serve as the evaluative dimensions for assessing acceptance mechanisms. This dual-framework approach enables a structured analysis of whether and how generational imprinting shapes the acceptance of AI-supported screening tools. A detailed description of the PCC framework relevant to this scoping review can be found in the section 'Inclusion and exclusion criteria'.

Objective and Review Question

The scoping review addresses the preliminary following question: Do cohorts from baby boomers to Generation Z differ in their perceptions of AI-supported CV screening processes based on semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking, and what expectations does this create for employers? Accordingly, the objectives of the scoping review are: (a) to examine the cohort-specific differences in PU and PEOU of AI-supported CV screening processes, using the integrative GCT and TAM frameworks, and (b) to identify knowledge gaps and make suggestions for future research initiatives.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Empirical primary studies are included in the scoping review. These come from peer-reviewed journals to ensure the methodological validity of the literature selection. In line with subject-specific

recommendations for scoping reviews, grey literature such as dissertations, conference papers, working papers from institutes, reports from government agencies and not-governmental organizations will be included. This approach follows the methodological necessity of focusing on specific literature sources while considering the multidimensional quality of non-peer-reviewed sources. In both cases, the sources must meet strict academic standards and the requirement of objectivity to preserve the exploratory purpose of the scoping review.

The quality assurance of grey literature is carried out using the AACODS checklist (Tyndall, 2008) to ensure a methodologically based evaluation of sources and to establish a consistent scientific standard. Each source is critically examined according to criteria relating to the dimensions of authority, accuracy, coverage, objectivity, date, and significance. The search for grey literature focuses on the ProQuest, and SSRN platforms. The specification of the inclusion and exclusion criteria is based on the PCC framework and is detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Population, concept, and context framework

	Inclusion criteria	Exclusion criteria
Population	<p>Literature focusing on various applicant cohorts defined by the GCT will be considered.</p> <p>Studies examining individual perceptions of applicants within the recruitment process will also be included.</p>	<p>Literature that does not define participants by birth years according to GCT or treats applicants as homogeneous group without age or cohort differentiation will be excluded.</p>
Concept	<p>AI-supported Recruitment, specifically implementing semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking methods.</p> <p>The concept encompasses the evaluation of Perceived Usefulness (PU) and Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) as defined by the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)(Davis, 1989).Although more recent technology acceptance frameworks such as TAM 2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003), and TAM 3 (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008) incorporate age as moderating variable, they treat it as an atheoretical demographic factor without specifying the mechanisms through which age-related differences in acceptance arise. This review</p>	<p>Evidence on recruitment processes that do not consider algorithmic pre-selection is excluded.</p>

	<p>therefore deliberately adopts the original TAM constructs on PU and PEOU (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000) and integrates them with GCT to provide a theoretically grounded explanation for cohort-specific acceptance patterns. While UTAUT captures that age moderates technology acceptance, the proposed integration of GCT and TAM aims to explain why this is the case, by associating cohort-specific value orientations and formative sociotechnical experiences to the evaluation dimensions of PU and PEOU.</p>	
Context	<p>The context is the screening stage within the hiring funnel.</p> <p>Targeting studies conducted in various countries, primarily focusing on Western Europe, North America, and Asia.</p>	<p>Evidence from domains, such as AI-supported onboarding or human resource development. Subsequent stages of the hiring process beyond screening will just be used to frame the hiring process to centering on the AI-supported screening process of the CV.</p>
Types of evidence sources	<p>Empirical studies and original research offering firsthand insights into the perception and application of AI-supported recruitment.</p> <p>Includes primary, secondary, or simulated data through quantitative (e.g., cross-sectional, longitudinal, or scenario-based experiments) and qualitative designs (e.g., interviews, surveys, focus groups).</p> <p>Systematic and narrative reviews are included to identify theoretical frameworks. Grey literature (e.g., research reports, dissertations, conference proceedings) evaluated using the AACODS framework is included to generate information.</p> <p>Only evidence published in the English language with no restrictions on publication date.</p>	<p>Editorials, commentaries, and forms of literature reviews that are not peer-reviewed publications are excluded.</p> <p>Literature reviews that are not published in peer-reviewed journals</p> <p>Non-peer-reviewed publications that fail to meet the AACODS quality standards.</p> <p>Empirical articles published in non-English languages will be excluded</p>

Methods

As a methodology for evidence synthesis, this scoping review aims to evaluate the breadth and nature of available evidence, identify existing research gaps, and define future priorities for scientific debate. To ensure a solid scientific framework and guarantee transparency and reproducibility, the study is conducted in accordance with the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI) framework and the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR). This methodological approach provides the basis for conducting the review (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Levac et al., 2010; Peters et al., 2020; Tricco et al., 2018). In addition, the research follows the proposed reporting guidelines and checklists of PRISMA-ScR and PRISMA-P (Shamseer et al., 2015).

Registration

The protocol will be registered in Zenodo.

Search strategy

In accordance with the JBI recommendation for the scoping review framework, the evidence search follows a three-stage approach. First, two independent reviewers conduct an initial screening of search terms and concepts within titles, abstracts, and keywords. This stage utilizes the ProQuest and SSRN platforms (and databases) for grey literature, as well as EBSCO, Scopus, and IEEE Xplore for peer-reviewed articles (Haddaway et al., 2015). The selection of database reflects the available institutional access. EBSCO provides broad coverage of social science and business literature, Scopus offers interdisciplinary and bibliometrically comprehensive coverage with substantial overlap with Web of Science (Falagas et al., 2008; Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020), and IEEE Xplore captures the technical and engineering perspectives relevant to AI-based recruitment systems. ProQuest and SSRN complement the search for grey literature. While Web of Science is not included due to institutional access limitations, the combination of Scopus and EBSCO is expected to provide sufficient coverage of the relevant evidence base. This limitation is acknowledged in the discussion.

Following this initial review, potential results are reconciled within the reviewer team to identify consensus and narrow the scope. To ensure methodological rigor, two reviewers evaluate the validity of the grey literature using the AACODS checklist (Tyndall, 2008). The AACODS checklist is primarily utilized in health sciences as an instrument for validating grey literature. Its application is justified by necessity to mitigate subjective bias in grey literature and to ensure an evidence-based assessment for the scoping review. Only sources that correspond with the AACODS checklist criteria are included in the scoping review. Detailed parameters are specified in the 'Inclusion and exclusion criteria section. Furthermore, the initial search serves to identify key terms for finalizing the comprehensive search strategy. A search conducted on Zenodo in March 2026 revealed that there are currently a few reviews on this topic, but none that are relevant. For the subsequent database search, a dedicated search strategy

was developed that defines preliminary key terms for the protocol (see Supplemental Materials: Appendix: 1-6). The search terms are specified in Appendix 1 (Table 2-5) and are combined using Boolean operators (OR, AND). Tentative search terminology for this scoping review protocol is presented in Box 1. Following keyword mapping, duplicates were removed, and relevant thematic terms were added to prepare the final search string for pilot testing. The validation of the protocol's search strategy involves an iterative process across four test runs in the Scopus database (Appendix 2: Table 6-8). The final string will be adapted for the EBSCO, IEEE Xplore, ProQuest, and SSRN platforms during the scoping review.

In each iteration, the first fifty results (sorted by relevance) were screened based on title, abstract, and keywords to progressively refine the terminology. During the pilot phase, only peer-reviewed articles were considered to ensure consistent technical terminology and to precisely calibrate recall and precision quotes. Expansion to additional document types will occur in the actual scoping review (see 'Inclusion and exclusion criteria') to allow for comprehensive evidence mapping without compromising the methodological rigor of the string validation. Relevant articles identified during the pilot tests were included in the list of 'Preliminary Articles' (Appendix 3: Table 9-11 and Appendix 4: 12-17). The preliminary final search string (Appendix 4: Table 18-20,22) was evaluated for logical consistency, syntax errors, and terminological completeness using the PRESS checklist (Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies) (McGowan et al., 2016). Since the PRESS checklist was primarily designed for systematic reviews (PICO approach), it has been adapted and labeled for the PCC approach specific to scoping reviews (Appendix 5: Table 21) There is an awareness that the PRESS checklist was developed as an evidence-based guideline for systematic reviews rather than explicitly for scoping reviews (PCC framework). However, since the focus is on search strategy quality rather than the explicit PICO or PCC framework questions, the PRESS checklist is utilized in both the protocol and the scoping review to ensure validation. The final search involves preliminary combinations of the terms 'human resource management', 'candidate', 'artificial intelligence', and 'recruitment' (Appendix 4: Table 18-20). It should be noted that the pilot tests conducted at the protocol stage are designed to calibrate the search string and do not yet represent the complete evidence base of the scoping review. The preliminary key articles serve primarily as benchmarks for recall and precision optimization. The identification of the full body of relevant literature, including studies that directly address the intersection of cohort-specific perceptions and AI-supported screening mechanisms, will be achieved through the comprehensive database search, supplemented by backward and forward snowballing during the primary execution phase of the scoping review.

In accordance with the inclusion criteria, the search is limited to empirical, peer-reviewed journal articles in English and validated grey literature. No restrictions are placed on publication dates or study design. Additionally, filtering by subject areas and manual review of the reference lists of included articles (backward citation searching) will be performed by one reviewer to identify additional relevant evidence. After two months (April 2026 – see Appendix 6 – Table 22), a final check was conducted to

determine whether new relevant peer-reviewed articles could be included, thereby ensuring that the latest findings were considered.

Box 1 List of search terms

	(Population)
	applicant OR candidate OR "generational cohort" OR "generational perspective" OR "age group" OR "generation gap" OR "baby boomer" OR "Generation X" OR millennial OR "Generation Z" OR " Gen Z" OR "digital native"
AND	
	(Concept)
	"artificial intelligence" OR discrimination OR "highly automated" OR "semantic matching" OR "cut-off threshold" OR TAM OR "technology acceptance model" OR "decision-making tools" OR "recruitment ethnicity"
AND	
	(Context)
	recruitment OR "human resource management" OR "CV screening" OR "resume screening" OR "human capital" OR "personnel selection" OR hiring OR "recruitment biases"

To ensure technical validity, the search strategy for the protocol was subjected to an expert review by an information specialist from the university (HTWG Konstanz). The evaluation focused on the precise application of database-specific syntax (Scopus) and logical integration of the PCC framework. The institution does not provide a formalized certification process for search strategies, validation was performed informally through a professional assessment aligned with the PRESS checklist. The resulting feedback was iteratively incorporated into the final search string.

The scoping review will utilize the snowballing methodology as proposed by (Jalali & Wohlin, 2012). This procedure, is used in systematic literature reviews (SLRs) and aligns with the PRISMA-ScR guidelines, facilitates the identification of additional key articles. The objective is to ensure the comprehensiveness of the evidence mapping and to address potential omissions in the initial database search. This process will be conducted by the reviewer for each identified database. In the current protocol, snowballing is deferred for the time being, as only preliminary articles have been screened. Since these do not yet constitute the final database of the scoping review, systematic backward and forward snowballing will be performed during the primary execution phase of the scoping review.

Evidence screening and selection

Initially, duplicates will be removed. This is followed by a title/abstract and full-text screening conducted independently by two reviewers based on the predefined 'inclusion and exclusion criteria' and the management software Covidence. Any discrepancies between the reviewers regarding an article's eligibility will be resolved through constructive discussion, involving a third reviewer where necessary. In accordance with the PRISMA-ScR standard (Tricco et al., 2018), a flowchart will be developed (see Appendix 6: Figure 1) to detail the search results, the planned screening process, and the

rationale for excluding sources. Furthermore, the appendix of the final scoping review will provide a comprehensive list of the full-text screening, documenting both included and excluded studies. Additionally, a quality appraisal (Hilton, 2024; Tricco et al., 2018; Zarin et al., 2017) will be performed to identify high-quality evidence and facilitate a critical discussion of the findings. While the results of this appraisal will be used for a more in-depth analysis of the subject matter, they will not lead directly to the explicit exclusion of studies, thereby preserving the breadth of evidence mapping characteristic of a scoping review.

Data extraction

In accordance with established academic standards, a predefined data charting form will be developed. This data charting form is pilot-tested during the review protocol stage and successively refined or updated during the primary investigation phase (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005; Levac et al., 2010; Tricco et al., 2018). This procedure ensures the generation of a logical and descriptive summary of the results, strictly aligned with the scoping review's objectives and research questions (Peters et al., 2020). The data charting forms are provided in the Supplementary Material (Appendices 1-6). These were validated through multiple pilot tests based on data generated from the Scopus search. The data charting forms capture information on study characteristics, key findings, and specifics of AI-supported recruitment as reported in the literature. During the pilot testing stage, thematically relevant articles were screened in iterative processes and tentatively added to the protocol. Furthermore, in the scoping review, two reviewers will extract data independently from the identified evidence and discuss the findings before the analysis and presentation. Any discrepancies regarding data extraction will be resolved through discussions or by involving a third reviewer.

Analysis and presentation of results

The characteristics of the included studies will be presented in tables and summarized through a narrative synthesis. For the systematic analysis, an integrative theoretical framework will be used, synthesizing Generational Cohort Theory (GCT) and the Technology Acceptance model (TAM). The first level of this framework utilizes GCT to identify cohort-specific value patterns and historical imprinting as key determinants (Mannheim, 1952; Strauss & Howe, 1991)². The second level applies the core TAM variables (PU and PEOU) to evaluate the acceptance mechanisms of AI-supported screening processes (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). On the third level, the synthesis examines whether cohort effects on PU and PEOU are mediated or contextualized by perceptions of transparency and fairness as reported in the included studies. These contextual dimensions are not treated as TAM

² There are various definitions of generations (Dimock, 2019)

core variables but as thematic categories that may emerge from the narrative synthesis and inform the identification of research gaps.

Two reviewers examine the articles selected for the scoping review to extract relevant data and structure it into emerging topics. These topics relate to cohort-specific aspects as well as the perception and acceptance of AI-supported CV screening processes. During the structuring process, new categories are generated inductively, or topics that have already been identified are restructured by reformulating and merging them. Once this process is complete, the reviewer discusses his findings with the second reviewer to get feedback and resolve any discrepancies regarding the topics they might have identified independently. The final scoping review will provisionally include a tabular summary or a diagram of each GCT topic in the TAM, based on the available data and using the framework developed by (Davis, 1989; Venkatesh & Davis, 2000). The results will focus on the descriptive structuring of the GCT and TAM approaches discussed in the existing literature, as well as the identification of implications for further research gaps where new primary research or semantic reviews are needed.

Discussion

AI-supported CV screening is a critical area of practical and theoretical interest (Hunkenschroer & Luetge, 2022). It is commonly understood as a management tool that has potential to increase efficiency and objectivity within the recruiting process while overcoming the limitations of traditional, keyword-based approaches (Köchling et al., 2021; Zheng et al., 2024). This suggests that algorithmic pre-selection is an emerging field with profound implications for theory and practice. The demand for organizations to demonstrate algorithmic transparency and fairness is steadily increasing, as applicants often perceive AI decisions as less fair than human judgments (Langer et al., 2019; Tursunbayeva et al., 2025). Given the growing risks of algorithmic bias associated with historically shaped data spaces transparent and methodologically verifiable selection strategies are therefore necessary to achieve the goal of ethical and valid recruiting. According to academic literature, the research field of scoping reviews is fundamental for mapping patterns of evidence-based practices, perception patterns, and acceptance factors in AI-supported recruiting. In addition, the scoping review aims to expand the existing literature by providing targeted pointers for the future research based on the identified research gaps within the evidence base.

Several limitations of this scoping review protocol should be acknowledged. First, the database selection does not include Web of Science due to institutional access constraints, which may result in the omission of relevant studies not indexed in Scopus, EBSCO, or IEEE Xplore. However, the substantial bibliometric overlap between Scopus and Web of Science mitigates this limitation (Falagas et al., 2008; Gusenbauer & Haddaway, 2020). Second, the specificity of the research focus on semantic matching and cut-off threshold ranking in combination with cohort-specific perceptions may yield a limited

number of directly relevant applicable studies. In this case, the scoping review will differentiate between directly relevant evidence and indirectly informing literature to ensure a meaningful evidence map. Third, the restriction to English-language publications may exclude relevant studies published in other languages.

The deliberate focus on TAM's core constructs PU and PEOU, while theoretically justified by their prevalence in the AI-recruiting literature and their complementarity with GCT, constitutes a theoretical delimitation of this review. Extended acceptance frameworks such as TAM 2 (Venkatesh & Davis, 2000), UTAUT (Venkatesh et al., 2003), and TAM 3 (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008) incorporate additional constructs, including social influence and facilitating conditions, that may further differentiate cohort-specific acceptance mechanisms. Future primary research building on this review's propositions should therefore examine whether these extended constructions provide incremental explanatory power, particularly through the qualitative exploration of acceptance dimensions that transcend PU and PEOU. It should be noted that GCT has faced significant criticism in the organizational behavior literature. Meta-analytic findings suggest that the observed generational differences in work values are often small and difficult to distinguish from age or time effects (Costanza et al., 2012; Dimock, 2019). The inherent confound between age, period and cohort, called APC-problem, poses a fundamental methodological challenge for cross-sectional generational research. The scoping review will acknowledge these limitations and uses GCT not as a causal explanatory model, but as a heuristic analytical lens for structuring the evidence base. The question of whether observed differences are attributable to cohort-specific effects or to alternative mechanisms is addressed by the primary empirical studies arising from the research agenda of the review.

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Author Contributions

The author designed the scoping review protocol, formulated the research questions based on the resulting PCC framework, developed and constructed the search strategy, performed the pilot tests, validated them using the PRESS checklist, and prepared the supplemental materials.

Conflict of Interest

The research was conducted independently, and no external parties were involved in the design of the protocol, the development of search strategy, or the interpretation of the preliminary results. The author declares that there are no known financial conflicts of interest or personal relationships that could influence the work described in this protocol.

Reference

- Ajjam, M.-H., & Al-Raweshidy, H. S. (2026). AI-driven semantic similarity-based job matching framework for recruitment systems. *Information Sciences*, 724, 122728.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2025.122728>
- Alonso, R., Dessí, D., Meloni, A., & Reforgiato Recupero, D. (2025). A novel approach for job matching and skill recommendation using transformers and the O*NET database. *Big Data Research*, 39, 100509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bdr.2025.100509>
- Arksey, H., & O'Malley, L. (2005). Scoping studies: Towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*, 8(1), 19–32.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1364557032000119616>
- Bogen, M., & Rieke, A. (2018). *Help wanted—An Examination of Hiring Algorithms, Equity, and Bias*. Upturn. <https://www.upturn.org/work/help-wanted/>
- Bower, A., Kitchen, S. N., Niss, L., Strauss, M. J., Vargas, A., & Venkatasubramanian, S. (2017). *Fair Pipelines* (arXiv:1707.00391). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1707.00391>
- Chouldechova, A., & Roth, A. (2018). *The Frontiers of Fairness in Machine Learning* (arXiv:1810.08810). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1810.08810>

- Chowdhury, G. G. (2003). Natural language processing. *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology*, 37(1), 51–89. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aris.1440370103>
- Costanza, D., Badger, J., Fraser, R., Severt, J., & Gade, P. (2012). Generational Differences in Work-Related Attitudes: A Meta-analysis. *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 27. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10869-012-9259-4>
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- Dimock, M. (2019, Januar 17). Where Millennials end and Generation Z begins. *Pew Research Center*. <https://www.pewresearch.org/short-reads/2019/01/17/where-millennials-end-and-generation-z-begins/>
- Falagas, M. E., Pitsouni, E. I., Malietzis, G. A., & Pappas, G. (2008). Comparison of PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar: Strengths and weaknesses. *The FASEB Journal*, 22(2), 338–342. <https://doi.org/10.1096/fj.07-9492LSF>
- Gusenbauer, M., & Haddaway, N. R. (2020). Which academic search systems are suitable for systematic reviews or meta-analyses? Evaluating retrieval qualities of Google Scholar, PubMed, and 26 other resources. *Research Synthesis Methods*, 11(2), 181–217. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrsm.1378>
- Haddaway, N. R., Collins, A. M., Coughlin, D., & Kirk, S. (2015). The Role of Google Scholar in Evidence Reviews and Its Applicability to Grey Literature Searching. *PLOS ONE*, 10(9), e0138237. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0138237>
- Hilton, M. (2024). JBI Critical appraisal checklist for systematic reviews and research syntheses. *The Journal of the Canadian Health Libraries Association*, 45(3), 180–183. <https://doi.org/10.29173/jchla29801>
- Horodyski, P. (2023). Applicants’ perception of artificial intelligence in the recruitment process. *Computers in Human Behavior Reports*, 11, 100303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chbr.2023.100303>
- Hunkenschroer, A. L., & Luetge, C. (2022). Ethics of AI-Enabled Recruiting and Selection: A Review and Research Agenda. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 178(4), 977–1007. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-022-05049-6>

- Jalali, S., & Wohlin, C. (2012). *Systematic literature studies: Database searches vs. backward snowballing*. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2372251.2372257>
- Köchling, A., Riazy, S., Wehner, M. C., & Simbeck, K. (2021). Highly Accurate, But Still Discriminatory. *Business & Information Systems Engineering*, 63(1), 39–54. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-020-00673-w>
- Langer, M., König, C. J., & Papathanasiou, M. (2019). Highly automated job interviews: Acceptance under the influence of stakes. *International Journal of Selection and Assessment*, 27(3), 217–234. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijsa.12246>
- Levac, D., Colquhoun, H., & O'Brien, K. K. (2010). Scoping studies: Advancing the methodology. *Implementation Science*, 5(1), 69. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1748-5908-5-69>
- Mannheim, K. (1952). The Problem of Generations. *Essays on the Sociology of Knowledge*, 276–322.
- McGowan, J., Sampson, M., Salzwedel, D. M., Cogo, E., Foerster, V., & Lefebvre, C. (2016). PRESS Peer Review of Electronic Search Strategies: 2015 Guideline Statement. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, 75, 40–46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclinepi.2016.01.021>
- Peters, M. D. J., Marnie, C., Tricco, A. C., Pollock, D., Munn, Z., Alexander, L., McInerney, P., Godfrey, C. M., & Khalil, H. (2020). Updated methodological guidance for the conduct of scoping reviews. *JBIM Evidence Synthesis*, 18(10), 2119–2126. <https://doi.org/10.11124/JBIES-20-00167>
- Rojas-Galeano, S., Posada, J., & Ordoñez, E. (2022). A Bibliometric Perspective on AI Research for Job-Résumé Matching. *The Scientific World Journal*, 2022(1), 8002363. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8002363>
- Shamseer, L., Moher, D., Clarke, M., Ghersi, D., Liberati, A., Petticrew, M., Shekelle, P., & Stewart, L. A. (2015). Preferred reporting items for systematic review and meta-analysis protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: Elaboration and explanation. *BMJ*, 349, g7647. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g7647>
- Strauss, W., & Howe, N. G. (1991). *Generations: The history of America's future, 1584 to 2069*. Harper Perennial.
- Tricco, A. C., Lillie, E., Zarin, W., O'Brien, K. K., Colquhoun, H., Levac, D., Moher, D., Peters, M. D. J., Horsley, T., Weeks, L., Hempel, S., Akl, E. A., Chang, C., McGowan, J., Stewart, L.,

- Hartling, L., Aldcroft, A., Wilson, M. G., Garritty, C., ... Straus, S. E. (2018). PRISMA Extension for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR): Checklist and Explanation. *Annals of Internal Medicine*, 169(7), 467–473. <https://doi.org/10.7326/M18-0850>
- Tursunbayeva, A., Fernandez, V., Gallardo-Gallardo, E., & Moschera, L. (2025). Artificial intelligence and digital data in recruitment. Exploring business and engineering candidates' perceptions of organizational attractiveness. *European Management Journal*, S0263237325000416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emj.2025.03.002>
- Tyndall, J. (2008). *HOW LOW CAN YOU GO? : TOWARD A HIERARCHY OF GREY LITERATURE*.
- Venkatesh, V., & Bala, H. (2008). Technology Acceptance Model 3 and a Research Agenda on Interventions. *Decision Sciences*, 39(2), 273–315. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-5915.2008.00192.x>
- Venkatesh, V., & Davis, F. D. (2000). A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science*, 46(2), 186–204. <https://doi.org/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). *User Acceptance of Information Technology: Toward a Unified View* (SSRN Scholarly Paper No. 3375136). Social Science Research Network. <https://papers.ssrn.com/abstract=3375136>
- Zarin, W., Veroniki, A. A., Nincic, V., Vafaei, A., Reynen, E., Motiwala, S. S., Antony, J., Sullivan, S. M., Rios, P., Daly, C., Ewusie, J., Petropoulou, M., Nikolakopoulou, A., Chaimani, A., Salanti, G., Straus, S. E., & Tricco, A. C. (2017). Characteristics and knowledge synthesis approach for 456 network meta-analyses: A scoping review. *BMC Medicine*, 15(1), 3. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12916-016-0764-6>
- Zheng, F., Zhao, C., Usman, M., & Poulouva, P. (2024). From Bias to Brilliance: The Impact of Artificial Intelligence Usage on Recruitment Biases in China. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 71, 14155–14167. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TEM.2024.3442618>